

Efficacy of fungicides and application methods for controlling blast (B1)

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B1 disease caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is endemic to the northeastern hill region of India, where it causes significant yield losses to upland and lowland rice. Chemical control by conventional fungicide sprays and dusts is difficult because of high rainfall and many rainy days during wet season. We tested other fungicide application methods such as seed treatment and seedling root-dip.

In 1982 wet season, we set up a fungicide trial with eight treatments and three replications in a randomized block design at Barapani farm, Shillong. Pusa 33 was transplanted in 3.5 × 2-m plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60-60-40 kg NPK/ha. Combinations of carbendazim, benomyl, IBP, and isoprothiolane were applied as seed treatment, root dip, and spray. Seed treatments were carbendazim and benomyl at 1 g ai/kg seeds; root dips were IBP .08% ai and isoprothiolane 0.04% ai; and sprays were carbendazim 0.05% and benomyl 0.05% ai, applied at 300-800 g ai of the fungicides in 600 to 800 litres water/ha.

Efficacy of fungicides and application methods for controlling B1 disease at Barapani, Shillong, India, 1982.

Fungicide, ^a application method	Dose (ai)	Efficacy (%)	
		Leaf B1	Neck B1
Carbendazim 50 WP (seed treatment)	1 g/kg seeds	40	34
Carbendazim 50 WP (seed treatment and sprays at PI and heading)	1 g/kg seeds + 0.5 g/litre	30	18
Benomyl 50 WP (seed treatment)	1 g/kg seeds	30	37
Benomyl 50 WP (seed treatment and sprays at PI and heading)	1 g/kg seeds + 0.5 g/litre	30	16
IBP 40 EC (12 h root-dip and sprays at PI and heading)	0.8 ml/litre	40	20
Isoprothiolane 40 EC (12 h root-dip and sprays at PI and heading)	0.4 ml/litre	20	6
Isoprothiolane 40 EC (sprays at tillering, PI, and heading)	0.4 ml/litre	20	8
0 (control)	—	70	32
CD (5%)	—	—	20

^aWP = wettable powder, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, PI = panicle initiation.

Data in the table show that seedling root-dip in isoprothiolane 40 EC for 12 h before transplanting, followed by one spray at panicle initiation and one at heading, can significantly reduce B1 incidence. A schedule of 3 sprays (20 d after transplanting, panicle initiation, and heading) of isoprothiolane was equally

effective. IBP 40 EC root-dip followed by one spraying at panicle initiation and one at heading, and carbendazim and benomyl either as seed treatment alone or as seed treatment plus spraying at panicle initiation and heading reduced foliar B1 but not neck B1. □

Effect of K on bacterial blight (BB) development

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To test the effect of K on BB development, we fertilized a soil sample containing 100 ppm K with 200 ppm N and 66 ppm P. One-third of the total N from urea was topdressed 7 d before panicle initiation. Five potash treatments (see table) in six pot replications were compared for effect on BB development and some other yield components. Three BB-susceptible IR8 seedlings were transplanted in each plot and inoculated with

Relation between different doses of K and response of BB-inoculated IR8 plants in t. aman season, 1983, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.^a

Treatment	Average lesion length (cm)		Average no. of		Average yield (g/pot)
	1st inoculation at maximum tillering	2d inoculation at flag leaf stage	fertile tillers	filled grains	
100 ppm K	30 a (7)	13 a (5)	81 a	71 b	34 a
183 ppm K	22 b (5)	8 b (5)	78 a	76 a	37 a
266 ppm K	20 bc (5)	6 b (5)	74 a	80 a	40 a
349 ppm K	19 bc (5)	6 b (5)	76 a	81 a	40 a
432 ppm K	16 c (5)	5 b (5)	78 a	79 a	43 a
CV%	12.6	34.0	13.6	7.4	12.4

^aData are averages of six replications. Figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P0.05 level. Values in parentheses are scores based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9.

Xanthomonas campestris pv. *oryzae* strain BXO9 at maximum tillering and at flag leaf stage by clipping.

Comparison of plants grown on treated soil and on soil with 100 ppm K showed that average lesion lengths both